

DCH README File Guidelines

Version 1.0.0

1. Keep it simple
2. Keep the README file with the dataset
3. Describe the dataset and its context
4. Document the internal structure of the dataset
5. Document file naming structure (including used vocabulary)

1 Keep it simple

The README file should be written as plain text or markdown (RFC 7764) with a simple and concise structure (e.g. this [template](#)). Do not try to fit the content of a full metadata profile into the README file, use a separate file in a structured metadata format for this.

2 Keep the README file with the dataset

The README file should be stored next to the dataset or in the top folder of the dataset.

3 Describe the dataset and its context

The README file should contain a description of the data and the context in which the set was collected. The description may contain data types, file format, legal information and any other information relevant for (re-)use or administration.

4 Document the internal structure of the dataset

The README file should contain a description of the internal structure of the dataset. It should be clear which information belongs where in the folder structure.

See: DCH Folder Structure Guidelines [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7452113](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7452113)

5 Document file naming pattern

Document the file naming pattern: describe the file name structure and the vocabulary used for different categories.

See: DCH File Naming Guidelines [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7447485](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447485)

See also: DCH README File Template 1.0.0 [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7452055](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7452055)